

Fluoro Complexes of Hexavalent Uranium Salts of the Series $[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]^{3-}$, Part II.

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In a previous communication¹ the isolation of a few fluoro complexes of the series $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]^-$ was reported in which the compound obtained by the reaction between $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ and $\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 20% HF was formulated as $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]_3 \cdot [\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{UO}_2\text{F}_5]$. It now appears that the compound may be better represented as a fluoro complex belonging to the series $[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]^{3-}$ i.e., the compound may be formulated as $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]$. In the heptafluoro diuranyl series only two compounds of the formulae $\text{M}_3[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7(\text{H}_2\text{O}_n)]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Na}(4\text{H}_2\text{O})^2$ and $\text{K}(2\text{H}_2\text{O})^3$ have been very recently reported. In this communication we are reporting the isolation of a few new complexes of this series with both inorganic and organic cations by a variety of methods.

The method of preparation of the $[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]^{3-}$ complexes is the same as the method of preparation of the $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]^-$ complexes described earlier¹. For the preparation of the salts with organic cations a solution of the organic base dissolved in 20% HF was added with stirring to a solution of $\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ also dissolved in the same acid. The precipitated compound was washed and dried as described earlier¹. meta-Chloroaniline, para-toluidine and para-anisidine gave the same compound $(\text{BH})_3 [(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]_n \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ with the uranium : organic base ratio = 1 : 1; 1 : 3; and 3 : 1. For the preparation of the salts with inorganic cations aqueous solutions of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ in excess were added to 20% HF solution of $\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The precipitation was almost quantitative. The precipitates were washed and dried as before. The analytical results of the compounds prepared are given in Table-1. The method of analysis was the same as described earlier¹.

The compound $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]$ was also obtained by the metathesis between the concentrated aqueous solution of hexamminecobalt (III) chloride and the salts of the series $[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]^{3-}$, e.g., $\text{K}_3[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^3$, $(m\text{-Cl-aniH})_3 [(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]$, $(p\text{-AniH})_3 [(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(p\text{-TolH})_3 [(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]$, and also with salts of the series $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]^-$ e.g., with $\alpha\text{-PicH}[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]^+$ and $\text{QH}[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]^+$. Some typical analysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]$ obtained from different compounds by the above method gave U = 56.84, 56.87, 56.95%; F = 15.94, 16.44, 16.10% and Co = 7.09, 7.14, 7.12%. This probably indicates the greater stability of the $[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]^{3-}$ ion and the lower solubility of its hexamminecobalt (III) salt.

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TABLE I

Compounds with their colour	%U	%F	%Co	%N	Solubility in water in gm. per lit. at 25°
1. [Co(NH ₃) ₆][(UO ₂) ₂ F ₇] Orange yellow	Calc. 57.07 Found 56.8	Calc. 15.95 Found 16.3	Calc. 7.07 Found 7.26	Calc. 10.07 Found 10.3	2.02*
2. [Co(en) ₃][(UO ₂) ₂ F ₇] Bright yellow	Calc. 52.22 Found 52.3	Calc. 14.58 Found 14.8	Calc. 6.49 Found 6.6		2.58
3. (<i>p</i> -AnisH) ₃ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₇].2H ₂ O Shining ash	Calc. 44.03 Found 43.6	Calc. 12.30 Found 12.0			12.8
4. (<i>p</i> -TolH) ₃ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₇] Brownish yellow	Calc. 47.75 Found 48.0	Calc. 13.35 Found 13.7			25.0
5. (<i>m</i> -Cl-aniH) ₃ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₇] Light yellow	Calc. 47.07 Found 46.9	Calc. 12.56 Found 12.7			14.7

Abbreviation :—en = ethylene diamine, *p*-Anis = para-anisidine, *p*-Tol = para-toluidine, *m*-Cl-ani = meta-Chloroaniline. *Solubility at 29°.

The formation of the ion [(UO₂)₂F₇]³⁻ from [UO₂F₃]⁻ was also indicated from studies with ion exchange resins. Dilute aqueous solution of α -PicH[UO₂F₃]¹ (approx. 0.025*M*) and Nic H[UO₂F₃]¹ (approx. 0.2*M*) (Nic = nicotinic acid) were separately passed through a column of Amberlite I.R.-120 (Na-form). The analysis of the eluate with both compounds gave Na : U : F = 3 : 2 : 7 (approximately). Portions of eluate were concentrated in a desiccator over fused CaCl₂. The crystals separated were collected and washed with ethanol and acetone and dried over H₂SO₄. The analysis of the compound corresponded to the formula Na₃[(UO₂)₂F₇].2H₂O (vide Table-II). These studies indicate that [UO₂F₃]⁻ in these compounds has been converted to the stabler [(UO₂)₂F₇]³⁻ in contact with the resin.

This sodium salt was also obtained by the metathesis of the salts α -Pic H[UO₂F₃]¹, *p*-Aminophen.H.[UO₂F₃]¹, Anth.H.[UO₂F₃]¹ of the series [UO₂F₃]⁻ and (*m*-Cl-aniH)₃[(UO₂)₂F₇], K₃[(UO₂)₂F₇(H₂O)₂]³ of the [(UO₂)₂F₇]³⁻ series with sodium perchlorate by trituration in presence of a little water. From the filtrate the sodium salt was precipitated by ethanol in sufficient excess. It was washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried over H₂SO₄. The analytical results are given in Table-II.

TABLE II

Analytical results of Na₃[(UO₂)₂F₇].2H₂O obtained by ion exchange and metathesis

Compound obtained from	%Na	%U	%F
(i) α -Pic.H[UO ₂ F ₃]**	9.26	61.0	17.8
(ii) Nic.H[UO ₂ F ₃]**	8.55	60.9	17.5
(iii) α -Pic.H[UO ₂ F ₃]	9.01	60.6	17.5
(iv) <i>p</i> -Amino.phen.H[UO ₂ F ₃]	9.24	61.3	17.7
(v) Anth.H[UO ₂ F ₃]	9.50	60.8	17.4
(vi) (<i>m</i> -Cl-aniH) ₃ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₇]	8.92	60.9	17.3
(vii) K ₃ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₇ (H ₂ O) ₂] ³	8.93	61.1	17.2

Na₃[(UO₂)₂F₇].2H₂O requires Na, 8.87; U, 61.17; F, 17.10%.

** By ion exchange.

The molecular conductance of an aqueous solution of $\text{Na}_3[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ having concentration $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ was 358 ohm^{-1} at 25° indicating it to be an uni-tervalent electrolyte. The other compounds of this series, namely $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3][(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]$ and $(m\text{-Cl-aniH})_3[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7]$ at the same dilution registered the molecular conductances as 291, 298 and 291 ohm^{-1} respectively at 22° .

The compounds with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ are very insoluble in water. The sodium compound which is yellow in colour is highly soluble in water. The compounds with organic bases are moderately soluble in water. All these compounds are insoluble in common organic solvents like ethanol and acetone. The solubilities of the compounds in water are given in Table-I.

The TGA curve of $\text{Na}_3[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_7] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was recorded in a manual thermo balance. 0.090 g of the finely powdered substance was heated at a rate of 2° per min. The substance began to lose weight slowly from about room temperature (35°). The weight loss curve indicated that the first water molecule was lost up to 140° (loss found 2.33%; calc. 2.31%) and the second water molecule was lost from 140° to 180° (loss found 4.65%; calc. for two water molecules 4.63%).

The infrared spectrum of the sodium salt was recorded on potassium bromide disc from 660 to 4000 cm^{-1} . It gave bands at 855 (w), 930 (vs), 1620 (vs) and $3600 \text{ (vs)} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (where w denotes weak band and vs denotes very strong band). It appears that the bands at 930 and 855 cm^{-1} are due to $\text{U}=\text{O}$ stretching. The other two bands are in the region of H-O-H bending and O-H stretching frequency.

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